

Table E.1. missing data in the three experimental sessions in the first study involving healthy occasional smokers		
	Comp vs. Baseline ¹	Reasons for missing data
Sham-vaping (n = 24)		One participant did not perform the sham-vaping session
Serum CC16		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	21 (87.5%)	Not enough serum (n=1); satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=2)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	13 (54%)	The "150 minutes after exposure" sample was introduced from the eleventh participants (n=10); satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1)
Urine CC16		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	19 (79%)	Not enough urine (n=1); below detection threshold (n=4)
Serum SP-D		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	22 (92%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=2)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	13 (54%)	The "150 minutes after exposure" sample was introduced from the eleventh participants (n=10); satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1)
Serum PG		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	19 (79%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=2); failure for technical reasons (n=3)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	10 (42%)	The "150 minutes after exposure" sample was introduced from the eleventh participants (n=10); satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1); failure for technical reasons (n=3)
TcpO₂/CO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	22 (92%)	Quality criteria not reached (n=2)
SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	20 (83%)	Quality criteria not reached (n=4)
Vaping without nicotine (n = 24)		One participant did not perform the vaping without nicotine session
Serum CC16		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	24 (100%)	No missing data
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	14 (58%)	The "150 minutes after exposure" sample was introduced from the eleventh participants (n=10)
Urine CC16		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	17 (71%)	Urine CC16 concentration was below the detection threshold (n=7)
Serum SP-D		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	24 (100%)	No missing data
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	14 (58%)	The "150 minutes after exposure" sample was introduced from the eleventh participants (n=10)
Serum PG		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	22 (92%)	Failure for technical reasons (n=2)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	12 (50%)	The "150 minutes after exposure" sample was introduced from the eleventh participants (n=10); failure for technical reasons (n=2)
TcpO₂/CO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	20 (83%)	Quality criteria not reached (n=4)
SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	17 (71%)	Quality criteria not reached (n=7)
Vaping with nicotine (n = 21)		Four participants did not perform the vaping with nicotine session
Serum CC16		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	18 (86%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1); below detection threshold (n=2)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	20 (95%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1)
Urine CC16		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	17 (81%)	Below detection threshold (n=4)
Serum SP-D		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	20 (95%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	18 (86%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1); failure for technical reasons (n=2)
Serum PG		
Baseline vs T30 (n - %)	15 (71%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1); failure for technical reasons (n=5)
Baseline vs T150 (n - %)	14 (67%)	Satisfactory vein puncture not achieved (n=1); failure for technical reasons (n=6)
TcpO₂/CO₂		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	19 (90.5%)	Quality criteria not reached (n=2)
SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	21 (100%)	No missing data

CC16, club cell protein-16; SP-D, surfactant protein-D; PG, propylene glycol; TcpO₂/CO₂, transcutaneous oxygen/carbon dioxide tensions;
SkBF, skin continuous microcirculatory blood flow
¹Number of data available for comparison between baseline

Table E.2. missing data in the two experimental sessions in the second study involving heavy smokers		
	Comp vs. Baseline ¹	Reasons for missing data
Sham-vaping (n = 10)		
Arterial blood analysis		
Baseline vs T5 (n - %)	10 (100%)	No missing data
Baseline vs T20 (n - %)	9 (90%)	Failure for technical reasons (n=1)
Pulse oximetry and heart rate		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	7 (70%)	Equipment rental from February 2018 (n=3)
TcpO₂/CO₂ / SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	5 (50%)	Equipment rental from February 2018 (n=3), quality criteria not reached (n=2)
Vaping without nicotine (n = 10)		
Arterial blood gas analysis		
Baseline vs T5 (n - %)	10 (100%)	No missing data
Baseline vs T20 (n - %)	9 (90%)	Failure for technical reasons (n=1)
Pulse oximetry and heart rate		
Baseline vs End (n - %)	7 (70%)	Equipment rental from February 2018 (n=3)
TcpO₂/CO₂ / SkBF		
Baseline vs post-exposure (n - %)	7 (70%)	Equipment rental from February 2018 (n=3)
TcpO ₂ /CO ₂ , transcutaneous oxygen/carbon dioxide tensions; SkBF, skin continuous microcirculatory blood flow		
¹ Number of data available for comparison between baseline		